

FEATURES OF KINDERGARTEN CHILDREN'S THINKING

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Abstract. Observation of certain phenomena, experience of their own actions with objects allow older preschool children to clarify their ideas about the causes of phenomena, to understand them more accurately through thinking.

By the end of preschool age, children begin to solve very complex problems that require an understanding of certain physical and other connections and relationships, the ability to use knowledge of these connections and relationships in new conditions. In this article, we will highlight the features of the thinking of children of kindergarten age.

Keywords: preschool age, thinking, child, attitude, demonstrative-figurative thinking.

Introduction. A six-year-old child can do a lot. But we should not overestimate his mental capabilities. The logical form of thinking, although it exists, is not yet typical, characteristic of him. His type of thinking is unique. The highest forms of visual-figurative thinking are the result of the intellectual development of a preschool child. Based on them, the child is able to distinguish the most important features, relationships between objects of surrounding reality. At the same time, preschool children not only understand schematic images, but also successfully use them. Teachers should take into account the position of psychologists about the leading role of practical activity in the development of children, the important role of visual-figurative and visual-motor thinking, and in particular about the thinking forms of preschool children.

Discussion. It should be noted that not only preschoolers, but also school-age children perform their own functions in the general process of mental development. At preschool age, the child should be prepared for the leading activity of primary school age - education. In this case, it is important to form the appropriate skills in the child. As shown in the research of A.P. Usova, the possession of these skills gives the child a "high level of cognitive ability". Its characteristic feature is the ability to distinguish an educational task and turn it into an independent goal of activity.

The child's thinking is associated with his knowledge. Two opposing tendencies are identified here. First, in the process of thinking, knowledge about the world around us is clarified, an expansion and deepening of the volume of concrete knowledge is observed. This stable knowledge forms the basis of the child's cognitive sphere. Second, in the process of thinking, a circle of vague, not entirely clear knowledge appears and grows, which acts in the form of assumptions and questions. This developing knowledge is a powerful stimulant of children's mental activity. In the process of interaction of these tendencies, the vagueness of knowledge decreases - they clarify and move on to concrete knowledge.

Conclusion and analysis. At preschool age, thinking forms also develop: understanding, judgment, conclusion, etc. All types of activities available to him can contribute to the development of thinking

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in a six-year-old child. All types of activities available to a six-year-old child can contribute to the development of thinking. At the same time, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for deep knowledge of the object.

The process of deepening knowledge of objects and phenomena inevitably leads to the emergence and growth of vague knowledge. Various games, design, modeling, drawing, reading develop in a child such thinking operations as generalization, comparison, abstraction, and establishing cause-and-effect relationships. Educational games with a child can improve thinking skills by 3-4 times.

Children's thinking goes through certain stages in the process of development. As noted by the famous child psychologist A.A. Lyublinskaya, the first tool for solving problems for a small child is his practical movement[1]. The child, whose toy helicopter has stopped spinning, starts to move without thinking and pulls, shakes, and turns the helicopter's rotor. Unable to achieve the desired result, he completely abandons further actions and turns to adults for help. Such thinking is called figurative-motor or practical: the task is given visually and is solved manually, that is, with practical action.

According to the concept of L.S. Vygotsky, during the transition from preschool to primary school age, the structure of consciousness is restructured, and due to this, all other mental processes are intellectualized[2].

In the development of thinking, a number of formal structures are distinguished that seem to be independent in content, which replace each other as the child grows up. Thinking begins to develop very rapidly in the period of kindergarten. This is due, firstly, to the relatively increased life experience of preschool children, secondly, to the well-developed speech of children during this period, and thirdly, to the ability of preschool children to act freely and independently[3].

Logical thinking begins to develop in older preschool children. All the possibilities for the development of logical thinking are revealed in children aged 6-7. Firstly, speech is sufficiently developed in children of this age, and secondly, concepts begin to take shape. In order for children to be able to think independently through words, without using images and imagination, they need to master concepts that reflect the most important features of real objects and phenomena[4]. In children, first, ideas expressed in words take shape. However, these ideas do not turn into concepts by themselves. These ideas can be used to structure concepts. Concepts and logical thinking forms based on them begin to take shape in the process of children mastering the foundations of knowledge in various fields. The consistent mastery of concepts is related to school education. After children have mastered concepts to a certain extent, they acquire the ability to think logically. In this case, children can solve the given problem intelligently.

During the preschool period, the child's free movement area expands. This is of great importance for the development of thinking. After preschool children have learned a lot in their experiences, they also begin to be interested in the internal properties of things. Therefore, they have many questions: What is this? Why is it like this? Who did it? Where did it come from? What does it do? This paves the way for the active and rapid development of thinking.

Children's questions should always be taken seriously. If a child cannot find an answer to his question or if adults do not pay attention to his question, his curiosity and inquisitiveness begin to wane. It is difficult to answer children's questions, because they ask questions about things and phenomena that they do not yet fully understand. The educator must answer and explain a number of questions from children, taking into account their age characteristics.

There are several reasons why children's questions are so interesting:[5]

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- 1) children reflect the surrounding objects and phenomena as they are, that is, as a whole, as in a picture;
- 2) they are not able to deeply analyze and synthesize the connection and causality between objects and phenomena;
- 3) they do not have a structured and mature scientific understanding of various natural and social phenomena;
- 4) children have very little life experience.

Developing elementary mathematical concepts through activities develops children's ability to make comparisons: it teaches them to draw conclusions and solve simple problems. Using cubes, circles, squares and strips, it is necessary to teach children to compare objects, distinguish similarities and differences, form groups of some objects and separate one from the group, divide objects into several equal parts, that is, into 2 and 4, and compare them.

When going to preparatory groups, you can develop a child's thinking by teaching them to count in order within ten and solve verbal problems. During excursions and walks, children's observation increases, they learn to compare different objects, analyze and synthesize. For example: children who go on an excursion to the garden, one child likens the legs of a turtle digging in the ground to a shovel, while another child likens them to the legs of an excavator. Such comparative reasoning has an active effect on the development of children's thinking.

As K.D. Ushinsky said, "Interest is complete thinking." Children are very curious. They strive to know the cause of events, to be aware of the secrets of everything. This is their interest, which is associated with the process of cognition.

Conclusion. It is necessary to use these interests in the development of children's thinking, because interest deepens the child's knowledge. Therefore, since the thinking of a young child in the preschool period is growing rapidly, its further development and development is one of the most important tasks facing children's institutions today.

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